

From Bias to Balance: Assessing Information Diversity in Google's AI Search

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Abstract

This paper delves into the transformative role of Generative AI in the realm of search engines, with a focus on Google Bard. At the forefront of this exploration is the question of how Google Bard, as an AI-powered tool, impacts the diversity of information presented in Google Search results. Employing the “search as research” methodology, this study critically examines the range and variety of topics, viewpoints, and sources across traditional and AI-powered Google SERPs. The research incorporates a comparative analysis of the representation of complex global issues such as the conflicts in Ukraine, Russia, Palestine, and Israel, investigating how AI reshapes information curation compared to traditional search algorithms. The findings reveal that while Google Bard extends the range of topics covered, it often streamlines complex narratives into generalized overviews, highlighting the persistence of mainstream biases and the challenges in achieving a truly diverse and unbiased information ecosystem. This study contributes to the broader academic discourse across Critical Search Engine Studies, Platform Studies, and Critical AI Studies, offering insights into the nuanced roles of AI in search engines, algorithmic transparency, and the ethical implications of digital information dissemination. The research underscores the need for ongoing scrutiny and ethical reflection in the development and deployment of AI technologies within search engines, advocating for a balanced approach that ensures technological innovation aligns with the goal of fostering a diverse, reliable, and comprehensive digital information landscape.

Introduction

The rise of Artificial Intelligence (AI) has led to transformative changes across various industries. AI technologies have become essential drivers in enhancing human activities, automating labor-intensive tasks, and fostering a wide range of advancements. Innovative Generative AI systems can generate new data that is similar to, but not exactly the same as, the data it was trained on (Dwivedi et al. 2023). The launch of large language-based models like ChatGPT in November 2022 and Google Bard in March 2023 has not only started the age of AI, but also represents “the tip of the iceberg when it comes to AI capabilities” (Lowden n.d.). In the digital realm, the use of AI and Generative AI opens to new frontiers of creativity and optimizes the use of digital media technology (Liang 2020). Tech magnates like Meta and Amazon have been heavily investing in AI, providing to users innovative services to gain profit from (Rikap 2023). However, a standout in this AI-centric turn is Google, which has reframed itself as an AI-first company (“Google I/O 2023: Making AI More Helpful for Everyone” 2023). Google has recently been experimenting with AI through the Search Labs initiative, an exploratory project that allows users to be early testers of new products and innovations of the company. One of Search Labs’ main initiatives is focused on building an AI-powered search engine, offered by Google Bard (i.e., a chat-based Generative AI tool from Google, powered by the generation large language model PaLM 2) (“Supercharging Search with Generative AI” 2023).

The increasing reliance on AI to curate and present information necessitates a careful examination of how these technologies impact the diversity of content presented to users. In the context of digital information retrieval, maintaining a diversity of information is paramount. Diverse search results ensure that users are exposed to a range of topics, viewpoints, and sources, fostering a well-rounded understanding, and preventing the dominance of singular narratives. This diversity is critical in the current landscape where digital platforms significantly influence public knowledge and discourse. By focusing on AI-powered search as offered by Google Bard through the Search Labs initiative, this study seeks to answer to the following research question: How does the implementation of Generative AI through Google Bard in Google Search results impact the information diversity of the results?

This study seeks to unpack the real-world implications of Google's AI-powered search, particularly focusing on Google Bard. It aims at investigating the impact of Generative AI's use in today's evolving information landscape. More specifically, it examines how its implementation on Google Search affects information diversity. Moreover, it looks at how Generative AI perpetuates or mitigates existing issues of relevance, filter bubbles and privileging mechanisms already associated to Google's search engine and its ranking algorithm. In the context of search engines, the use of Generative AI poses intriguing questions about the nature of the content presented to users. Specifically, how it might affect the diversity and range of information provided in response to a given query. In its first demo in February 2023, Google Bard produced inaccurate information, plummeting Google's shares and raising concerns and critiques regarding the use of AI to power or replace search engines (Vincent 2023). Google Search holds a significant market share in the search engine ecosystem (Ridgway 2023). With billions of queries processed daily, its influence on knowledge acquisition is undisputed. Ongoing academic debate focuses on Google Search algorithm's ranking ability, its implicit biases, and its possibilities of providing diverse and relevant information. Previous studies by Noble (2018) and Steiner et al. (n.d.) already exposed the latent biases embedded in Google Search algorithm, and how search engines tend to lack information diversity. Further studies have highlighted how search engines do not treat information equally, privileging specific sources and viewpoints (Rogers 2023), favoring trendy topics over comprehensive overviews (Gillespie 2014), and limiting exposure to diversified perspectives by enclosing users into ideological filter bubbles (Pariser 2011). However, there is a scarcity of research exploring these phenomena in the era in which AI represents the future of search engines. This study seeks to fill that gap by evaluating the early impacts of Google Bard on information diversity. This is not only relevant to academic discourse but also has wider cultural implications, affecting how societies access, process, and trust information in the digital age.

This paper starts by reflecting on existing literature from three academic domain relevant to this discussion: Search Engine Studies, Platform Studies, and Critical AI studies. The contribution from these three domains is crucial for a comprehensive analysis that not only dissects the new mechanics that Google Bard's Generative AI brings into Google Search, but also anticipates its effects on information retrieval and knowledge acquisition. Informed by precedent approaches to the study of Google's algorithm and its ranking capabilities, this paper employs the "search as research" method, running a set of selected

queries both through traditional Google Search engine and AI-powered search engine via Search Labs. By analyzing the informational diversity in response to a diverse array of queries, this study aims to uncover any shifts in content variety, the privileging of specific sources, or the exposition to a narrow spectrum of perspectives. Finally, findings are exposed together with observations on points of interest. This paper suggests that even though the implementation of Generative AI as offered by Google Bard in Google Search Engine appears promising, it is still far from being a solution to search engines' lack of diversity, conversely perpetuating issues of relevance, privileging, and filter bubbles. This thesis contributes to ongoing debate on Google Search algorithm and analyzes the broader implications of AI-powered digital platforms by investigating the initial outcomes of the AI-powered Google Search. Thus, it provides a context for discussing the evolution of future search engine technologies and the possible directions they might take. Furthermore, this research offers valuable insights that could guide stakeholders and policymakers in refining AI technologies to enhance the diversity and quality of search engine results.

Theoretical Framework

When Google released PageRank in 1998, extensive debates focused on the phenomenon of “Googlization” (Mager, Norocel, and Rogers 2023). This paper draws upon seminal works in the fields of Critical Search Engine Studies, Platform Studies, and Critical AI Studies. This study not only synthesizes these diverse strands of scholarship, but also situates them within the innovative method of “search as research” as articulated by Rogers (2013), thereby offering a holistic view of how digital platforms and AI shape – and are shaped by – the complexity of social relations and cultural dynamics in an increasingly interconnected world.

Googlization and the critique of search engines

The concept of “Googlization” has become a cornerstone in understanding the transformative influence of search engines on information access and dissemination. This phenomenon is understood by scholars as Google’s vast influence not just on search results, but also on our behaviors, perceptions, and knowledge structures (Vaidhyathan 2012). Early research from the field of Critical Search Engine Studies laid the groundwork for understanding Googlization, delving into how search engines index web pages. Lawrence and Giles (1998, 1999) highlighted the disparities in search engine indexing, particularly emphasizing the low coverage of web pages compared to the deep web. By conducting a

comparative analysis across leading search engines, their research introduced the idea that heavily linked websites dominated the search rankings. This notion was further explored and defined as “Googlearchy” later by Hindman et al. (2003), through the study of search engine rankings and the analysis of web structure. As Google evolved, a notable shift occurred towards personalization and commercialization within its search engine framework. This paradigm shift significantly altered user traffic dynamics, augmenting the importance of ranking on first page on Google. Studies using eye-tracking experiments on Google result pages highlighted the deep trust users have in Google’s ability of ranking and presenting information (Pan et al. 2007), stressing even more the need for a critical examination of its search algorithm. Battelle (2011) eloquently discusses the implications of this shift, noting how it redefined the value associated with top search engine results, both for advertisers and content providers. Furthermore, Pariser’s discussion on filter bubbles (2011) introduced a critical dimension to the understanding of personalized search results. Pariser’s concept of filter bubbles – where algorithms create echo chambers of content based on user preferences – had sparked significant debate on the impact of personalized search results on information diversity and public discourse. This work is instrumental in understanding the broader implications of algorithm-driven content curation and its role in shaping user experiences and perceptions.

Over time, researchers have increasingly integrated computational analysis of search algorithms with socio-cultural critiques, striving to untangle the intricate web of search engine operations and their wider societal repercussions. This shift highlighted the critical need for algorithmic transparency in search engines and the challenges posed by biases embedded within these algorithms. Follow-up studies have delved deeper into the implications of biases within Google’s search algorithms (Noble 2018, Rogers 2023). Noble’s work underscores the often-overlooked societal consequences of seemingly neutral algorithms, revealing the perpetuation of stereotypes and inequalities through search engine results (2018). This critical perspective on algorithmic biases challenges the conventional understanding of search engines as impartial tools, highlighting the need for greater scrutiny and ethical considerations in their design and operation. Complementing the critical perspectives offered by Noble (2018), Rogers’ work (2023) presents another significant dimension to the understanding of “Googlization” and its implications within Critical Search Engine Studies. Rogers’ research (2023) focuses on the operational and ethical facets of search engine outputs, scrutinizing the algorithmic decisions that govern what information

becomes visible and how it is ranked. By critically evaluating the output of search engines, Rogers contributes to a deeper understanding of how digital gatekeepers influence public knowledge and discourse. His work underscores the necessity for transparency and accountability in search algorithms, pointing towards the need for a more equitable digital information ecosystem. Expanding upon these operational and ethical aspects of search engine outputs, the study by Steiner et al. (2020) further expands our understanding of “Googlization” and its implications. Their work takes a deep dive into the practical outcomes of algorithmic decisions by examining the diversity of content presented by search engines on political issues in Germany through the examination of the first ten search engine results. It demonstrates that diverse information in search engine results is possible, but hardly achievable by looking only at first results, and therefore calls for more algorithmic transparency and better policies. The emphasis on algorithmic transparency and the need for diverse information resonates with the critical examination of search engine algorithms discussed in the works of Noble (2018), Rogers (2023), and others.

Beyond Google: Platform Studies

The field of Platform Studies has emerged from this foundational debate, concerning how digital platforms can be interpreted both as technological infrastructures and socio-cultural mediators, while influencing content generation, distribution, and reception. Jean Burgess’s work (2021) on platformization provides a critical foundation for understanding these phenomena. Her research, as outlined in “Platform Studies” (Burgess 2021), delves into the coevolution of platform technologies, business models, and user cultures. Burgess emphasizes the symbiotic relationship between online creators, communities, and digital media platforms, such as Google, YouTube, and Facebook, highlighting how these platforms shape – and are shaped by – the content and interactions they host. This perspective allows for an in-depth examination of the complex dynamics at play within the digital media ecosystem. Tarleton Gillespie delves deeper into these dynamics by analyzing the operational aspects of platforms (2014). Gillespie focuses on the mechanisms of algorithmic curation and content moderation within platforms. His analysis critically examines the social and cultural implications of algorithmic processes that determine what content becomes visible and influential (Gillespie 2014). Gillespie’s scrutiny of these processes reveals the complexities and often opaque nature of algorithmic decision-making, which significantly shapes public discourse and access to information. Transitioning into the age of AI, it becomes crucial to study and understand the consequences of the use of these technologies within the platform

ecosystem. On this note, Liang's study (2020) delves into the integration of AI within digital media platforms. This research highlights how AI technologies are not just auxiliary tools but are integral to the functionality of platforms like Google, YouTube, and Facebook. It underscores the transformative role of AI in automating and enhancing content generation and interaction, by conceptualizing a platform where AI significantly enhances media content production (Liang 2020). While the role of AI in enhancing digital media platforms seems promising, it also raises important questions about the implications of this innovation, especially under ethical and societal points of view.

Powering Platforms with AI: Critical AI Studies

The advent of Critical AI Studies adds to this discourse by bringing attention to the multifaceted dimensions of AI-driven platforms. Foundational work of this field, David J. Gunkel's "The Machine Question" (2012) challenges conventional perceptions of AI and robotics. Gunkel's work (2012) interrogates the ethical status and moral consideration of intelligent machines, pushing the boundaries of how we understand and interact with AI technologies. Therefore, Critical AI Studies stand at the forefront of examining the intricate implications of artificial intelligence (AI) in digital platforms, focusing on the ethical dimensions of algorithmic bias and fairness 12/12/23 5:00:00 PM. This field interrogates the consequences of the development, deployment, and implementation of AI technologies into the fabric of society (Gunkel 2012). Scholars argue that AI systems, far from being neutral entities, "both reflect and produce social relations and understanding of the world" (Crawford 2021). Crawford's investigation delves into the ethical dimensions of AI, uncovering the hidden costs of data bias, and calls for a more responsible approach to AI development. The advent of Generative AI raised even further concerns. The risks and challenges associated with these technologies are currently being extensively discussed. The work by Chen, Fu, and Lyu (2023) identifies key challenges of this innovation, exploring its impact in areas such as privacy, bias, toxicity, misinformation, and intellectual property rights – and suggests several mitigation strategies. With the growing interest in Generative AI, more studies started looking into specific models, their capabilities, and their ethical implications. The study by Aydin (n.d.) evaluates the use of generative AI in academic literature review, by using Google Bard to generate content around academic articles and critically evaluating it. This study highlights the capabilities and limitations of AI in producing academic content, revealing challenges in achieving originality and academic validity. In a parallel thread, Fostikov (2023) shares initial impressions of using ChatGPT. She explores ChatGPT's

diverse applications across scientific fields and the ethical concerns they raise, calling for safeguards against misuse. In the digital realm, this interest translates into a debate on the implications of AI-powered digital platforms, especially in terms of algorithmic bias and fairness (Mohamed, Png, and Isaac 2020). The research by Mohamed, Png, and Isaac (2020) critically examines how AI algorithms can perpetuate societal biases, highlighting the necessity for ethical frameworks in AI development. This work aligns with already existing concerns around algorithms, offering a complementary perspective on the need for transparency and accountability in forthcoming AI technologies and their implementation on platforms. Building upon these critical foundations, this study situates itself at the intersection of Critical Search Engine Studies, Platform Studies and Critical AI studies. By focusing on Google's latest foray into AI-driven search capabilities, this research seeks to contribute meaningfully to the ongoing discourse on the ethical, cultural, and informational implications of AI-powered search engines.

Concepts

In analyzing the impact of Generative AI on information diversity within Google Search results, it is crucial to delineate the concept of **information diversity**. Drawing from Stark and Geiß's study on the diversity of results in search engines (2020), information diversity is operationalized as the range and variance in topics, viewpoints, and sources represented within a defined information ecosystem. This concept is pivotal in understanding how algorithmic modifications, particularly the integration of Generative AI, can either foster a rich, multifaceted information landscape or, conversely, engender a narrow, monolithic information spectrum. In this context, the concept of **relevance** is also fundamental for measuring information diversity of results. As Gillespie (2014) states, algorithms – both on social networking sites and on search engines – define the knowledge that is accessible to us, and how to familiarize ourselves with it. They determine what is relevant, yet in a strictly algorithmically constructed sense, tied to terms like “popularity” and “newsworthy”, different from our human reasoning of it (Gillepsie 2014). This approach can sometimes lead to a narrow set of results, privileging certain sources or viewpoints and thus diminishing information diversity. With Generative AI, there is potential to redefine relevance. Instead of relying solely on popularity metrics, AI can consider a broader set of factors, including the user's intent and the contextual richness of the query. This could lead to a more diverse set of search results, encompassing a wider array of topics, viewpoints, and sources. However, these systems tend to present information as an easy-to-read story, and users “might not be

aware that other answers are possible” (Dwivedi et al. 2023). Therefore, there is also the risk that AI could inadvertently create **filter bubbles**, another concept that is worth considering in relation to information diversity. Pariser (2011) describes them as the risks posed by platforms – and in particular search engines – personalization mechanisms of isolating users into ideological bubbles, in which they are exposed to recurrent and specific information and viewpoints, lacking the exposition to more diverse voices. With the implementation of Generative AI into Google Search, filter bubbles could limit exposure to diverse viewpoints, ironically reducing information diversity in the name of relevance. In this context, it becomes crucial to scrutinize whether the implementation of Google Bard not only contributes to the formation of these filter bubbles but also whether it reinforces the mechanisms of **privileging** often associated to traditional search algorithms (Rogers 2023). Roger’s work (2023) highlights the latter as the prioritization of specific information types, sources, or viewpoints over others, effectively being the antithesis of information diversity. In this study, the intersection of information diversity, relevance, filter bubbles, and privileging mechanisms forms the core analytical framework for assessing the impact of Generative AI on Google Search, revealing how these intertwined concepts influence the richness and variety of information presented in search results.

Methodology

This study employs the “search as research” method as explained by Rogers (2013). The “search as research” method has been widely used to research search engines like Google (Noble 2018, Rogers 2023).

Doing AI critique with Google: the search as research method

The “search as research” method employed in this paper envisions search engines not as neutral technologies, but as “socio–epistemological machines, authoring source standing for a given subject matter” (Rogers 2013, 97). They determine what information is deemed relevant and what is marginalized. As Roger (2013) suggests, the analysis of search results, algorithms, and ranking mechanisms can uncover biases and preferences embedded within digital platforms. This method involves critically examining how search engines prioritize information, the nature of the content they surface, and the potential impacts on public knowledge and discourse. Several studies have employed “search as research” methodologies. For example, in his study on Google’s “filter bubbles”, Pariser (2011) uses a similar approach to analyze how personalized search results create echo chambers of

information, influencing users' perception of the world. Noble's "Algorithms of Oppression" (2018) also aligns with this method, examining how search algorithms perpetuate racial and gender biases. These works employ search engine data to critique and analyze the societal implications of algorithmic decision-making.

In the context of AI Studies, this approach takes on new dimensions. The work by Aydın (n.d.) adapts a similar methodology to assess the capabilities of AI in generating academic literature reviews. Aydın's study (n.d.) critically examines the outputs of Google Bard, an AI-driven tool, in synthesizing and paraphrasing academic content, thereby evaluating the influence of AI in shaping academic knowledge. Similarly, the study by Chen, Fu, and Lyu (2023) dives into the implications of AI-generated content, scrutinizing how AI models might perpetuate biases or misinformation. This work reflects the "search as research" approach by using the outputs of AI systems to analyze broader issues like privacy, intellectual property rights, and the ethical use of AI. By adapting one of the core methods employed in the academia for the study of search engines to the new dimension of AI-powered search, this paper seeks to contribute with novel insights into the understanding of how AI algorithms redefine information retrieval. It aims to bridge the gap between traditional search engine analytics and the burgeoning field of AI, providing a critical analysis of the implications for information accessibility, diversity, and the dynamics of user interaction in the digital age.

Research design

Previous studies employing the "search as research" method often perform query design purportedly to obtain stereotypical, racist or discriminatory results (Rogers 2023). However, since the aim of this research is not to explore algorithmic bias but information diversity as the range of topics, viewpoints and sources presented, its analysis is focused more on the breadth and depth of content rather than its ethical and moral implications.

For this reason, query designed is performed by choosing broad terms instead of more specific ones. This is important to: 1) ensure that the datasets obtained are representative of general queries, 2) yield as diverse results as possible, 3) avoid implicit biases, 4) use queries fitting the limitations posed by the Search Labs experiment. Moreover, it ensures that findings are relevant and applicable in a real-world context. The queries are chosen in relation to current global issues, more specifically to the upsurging conflicts between Ukraine

and Russia and Palestine and Israel. These issues are actively being discussed and searched for, which means that the search results are more likely to reflect the current capabilities and tendencies of the search algorithms. High search volume indicates that these issues are of significant interest to the public, making them ideal subjects for studying the diversity of information provided by search engines. Also, conflicts are often complex, have multiple narratives and viewpoints, making them even more interesting for an analysis comprehensive of topics, viewpoints, and sources. Four queries are selected: “Ukraine”, “Russia”, “Palestine” and “Israel”. By selecting two sets of related but distinct queries, it is not only possible to draw comparisons within a single conflict, but also to spot intersections and understand how specific issues are linked and presented by Generative AI in search.

The chosen queries are run on a single Google product: Web Search. As the SearchLab experiment is available only to users situated in the United States, both searches are run by using a VPN set to the US. Search is performed on traditional Google Search first, in an incognito window. The queries are conducted using specially prepared research browsers. These are freshly installed browser instances that are not logged into any Google account. Simultaneously, the same queries are run in the SearchLab experimental setting available for Chrome users. Therefore, logging in a proprietary Google Account is required. For this reason, a dedicated Google Account was specifically created for research purposes and had no prior search history or personalized data associated with it, thus ensuring that the search results obtained were as close as possible to what a typical, first-time user of Google might experience. In this experimental setting, the result pages obtained are similar to traditional Search Result Pages (SERPs), yet sources retrieved and their order may vary. Moreover, the user is also provided with a snippet of text at the top of the results generated by Google Bard, as a comprehensive overview of the most relevant information related to the query (see Figure 1). The top ten results both for traditional search and AI-powered search – including the AI-Generated text snippets – are collected through screenshots.

While traditional studies of Search Engine Results Pages (SERPs) often consider results both above and below the fold, this research places a particular emphasis on the content above the fold (i.e. the very first part of the screen when running a query on Google Search without scrolling). This focus is rooted in user behavior patterns indicating that a significant majority of users do not scroll beyond the first page of results, often making their choices based on the information immediately visible upon the query result display (Pan et al.

2007). With the advent of AI-driven search engines like Google Bard, this becomes even more significant. AI innovations, particularly Bard-generated text, have transformed SERPs by replacing typical “knowledge panels” (i.e., information boxes that appear on Google’s search results page when searching for entities - people, places, organizations, things - that are well-known and have information available in Google’s Knowledge Graph) with AI summaries at the top, reshaping user’s initial interactions and impressions. Accordingly, the display technique in reporting findings is to compare screenshots of content above the fold for traditional search and screenshots of top result pages for AI-powered search – together with the text generated by Bard – for each of the queries selected. For example, the screenshot of the content above the fold for the query “Ukraine” on traditional Google Search is placed right next to the screenshot of the content for the same query on AI-powered Google Search (see Figure 1, Figure 2). It is to note that features below the fold like “People also ask” or “Top Stories” are not to be analyzed in this paper. With this technique I aim at exploring the content the user is first presented with at the moment of search. This investigation represents the first, general layer of analysis of this study.

Figure 1: content above the fold in Google Search Result Page for the query “Ukraine”

Figure 2: content above the fold in AI-powered Google Search Result Page for the query “Ukraine”

Subsequently, to identify the impact of Generative AI on information diversity, each source ranking in the top ten results in traditional SERPs, AI-powered SERPs, and Bard-generated text, is analyzed and classified in an Excel spreadsheet. The positioning of the content itself is not being analyzed in this paper, but only the nature of it as present in the first page. An inductive content analysis is performed to explore, make understandable and categorize the information presented to the user on the result pages. The units of analysis selected are the source title, the content of the website itself (accessed through the URL), and the hosting website or organization. The following variables – derived from the operationalization of the concept of information diversity – are selected for the analysis: 1)

Topic: The main subject or theme of the search result; 2) **Viewpoint:** The perspective or stance presented within the result; 3) **Source:** The originating website or organization. The first and the second variables are retrieved from the analysis of the source title and content, while the third variable is directly derived from the domain in the URL. The creation of the coding scheme was progressive, repeating the assignation of codes several times to polish and consolidate them. Along the way, some codes were relaxed or newly expanded ones were developed. In this coding process, it is pertinent to acknowledge the unique nature of Wikipedia as a source. Unlike traditional singular-authored sources, Wikipedia is a crowd-sourced and consensus-based platform. This means that each entry on Wikipedia is typically not the product of a single author or viewpoint, but rather a compilation of multiple contributors' perspectives. Therefore, when Wikipedia is referenced in this analysis, it is important to consider it as a source comprising multiple viewpoints. The final coding scheme is detailed in the appendix and provides further explanation for the assignation of specific codes to each variable. The final coding scheme iterates only over the variables "Topic" and "Viewpoints" as they are the only one retrieved through the interpretation of the results. I employ a detailed and methodical approach to visualizing information diversity in search engine results pages (SERPs). For every query, I generate individual bar charts to represent and compare the single appearances of three key variables – topics, viewpoints, and sources – across traditional SERPs, AI SERPs and Bard-generated text (see Figure 10, Figure 11). Moreover, I create specific bar charts also for the breakdown allows for content "above the fold", to understand the variety of information immediately presented to users (see Figure 9). Furthermore, I create single doughnut charts to represent – respectively – the distribution of topics and viewpoints for each query both across traditional SERPs and AI SERPs – according to the top 10 sources retrieved (see Figure 12, Figure 14). Distribution of sources is observed instead through color coding, to observe in the specific which sources predominated over the others (see Figure 16). Finally a matrix chart is created from the content analysis of the text generated by Bart both for topics, viewpoints and sources to measure their presence over the four queries (see Figure 13, Figure 15, Figure 17).

Analysis

In this analysis, I delve into the complexities of how information is presented across traditional Google SERPs, AI powered SERP and text generated by Google's Bard AI. This section will not only present findings but also critically engage with the data to unravel the nuances behind the core research question of this paper: How does the implementation of

Generative AI through Google Bard in Google Search results impact the information diversity of the results? By examining the representation of topics, the variety of viewpoints, and the spectrum of sources, I aim to understand the consequences on information diversity brought by the implementation on Google Search of Bard AI, and its implications for the future of information retrieval and knowledge acquisition. Overall, the analysis of the findings underscored the complex interplay between the types of topics presented, the viewpoints expressed, and the sources cited. AI-generated results provided a more diverse mix, revealing a more balanced distribution of topics in AI Generated SERPs and a wider variety of sources. However, it was also noticed how traditional SERPs tended to prioritize established information sources and current events, while AI SERPs present a more diverse content spread, potentially lacking context, quality or trustworthiness. In the context of the examination of the content above the fold, this resulted in an increase in topics and sources variation, but a potential risk of lack of depth and the erosion of common informational ground. Indeed, users are presented with different pictures of reality between each other considering that the text generated by Bard depends on user's input and varies at every iteration. In the following section, I delve into a more detailed analysis of the content above the fold. After a general overview of topics, viewpoints, and sources across different SERPs, I present findings in relation to each of the variables. I conclude by summarizing main insights before discussing the implications of these results in relation to the concepts of information diversity, relevance, filter bubbles and mechanisms of privileging delineated above.

Initial impressions: content above the fold

The content above the fold presents more differences between Traditional SERPs and AI-powered SERP. Traditional Google searches tend to offer a constrained array of information (Figure 3). Queries such as "Ukraine" bring forth basic suggestions like "news," "map," and direct Wikipedia entries, suggesting a prioritization of immediacy and accessibility (Figure

1). Moreover, it supplements the user experience with knowledge panels. For instance for the query “Russia” (Figure 3) a carousel of images, interactive maps, and flag representations provides a visual and geographical context to the user.

Figure 3: content above the fold in Google Search Result Page for the query “Russia”

Figure 4: content above the fold in AI-powered Google Search Result Page for the query “Russia”

However, it also presents a link to a YouTube video whose cover says that Russia’s victory (referring to the ongoing war with Ukraine) would be a tragedy. This immediate presentation of multifaceted information – from geographical and linguistic to political– furnishes the user with a complex picture, specifically focused on news and current events. Conversely, AI-powered searches exhibit a more sophisticated array of suggestions under the search bar, including nuanced phrases like “news today now live” and specific queries such as “time, president,” , and a varied tapestry of topics and sources in the text snippet generated by Bard that often directly mirrors the content found in traditional SERP knowledge panels (Figure 4). Also for the query “Israel” (Figure 6) the content generated by Bard repeat word by–word specific sentences included instead in the snippet of text taken from Wikipedia in traditional SERP (Figure 5).

Figure 5: content above the fold in Google Search Result Page for the query “Israel”

Figure 6: content above the fold in AI-powered Google Search Result Page for the query “Israel”

However, these AI-curated snippets extend beyond mere reproduction, presenting a more rounded view that includes geographic, political, and diplomatic aspects. Indeed, in the case of the query “Russia” while only the first few sentences of the generated text reference Wikipedia, the rest is reimagined and draws not only from the first lines, but from the full article, touching on several topics (Figure 4).

The “Palestine” query starkly contrasts with other traditional SERPs, dominated by topicality and focused primarily on news and recent developments (Figure 7). The layout above the fold leaves limited room for alternative narratives or diverse content types, skewing the user’s first encounter with the topic towards current events and media coverage. This prioritization is less evident in AI SERP, where Bard AI often stitches together a diverse narrative from multiple aspects of the query topic, indicating a potentially less biased and more holistic approach to information curation (Figure 8).

Figure 7: content above the fold in Google Search Result Page for the query “Palestine”

Figure 8: content above the fold in AI-powered Google Search Result Page for the query “Palestine”

As the chart shows, AI SERPs outrank Traditional SERPs in terms of topics and sources (reported in the carrousel next to the text in the content above the fold in AI SERPs) almost across all queries but in the query “Palestine” (Figure 9). Content above the fold in AI SERP is almost completely retrieved from Wikipedia. Scrolling down the fold, this changes, as Bard starts citing the rest of the sources mentioned in the carrousel.

Figure 9: bar chart showcasing single appearances of topics, viewpoints and sources in the content above the fold for each query in Traditional SERPs and AI SERPs

There is therefore a marked difference in how each search result page guides the user's initial interaction. Traditional SERPs appear to prioritize established information sources and breaking news, reflected in the prominence of Wikipedia and news outlets. In contrast, AI SERPs strive for breadth, pulling together diverse information from various sources – even with the constant of Wikipedia referenced in almost all queries – including government sites and more detailed multimedia content, before the user ever scrolls.

Scrolling down: traditional vs. AI-powered SERPs

The analysis of topics, viewpoints and sources across the top 10 results both in traditional SERPs and AI SERPs is revealing. The difference in information diversity immediately visible in the content above the fold thanks to the text generated by Bard almost disappears when looking at overall search results categorization. The bar chart summarizing the single appearances of topics, viewpoints and sources across queries in the entire result pages immediately showcase almost equal trends among the search result pages (Figure 10).

Figure 10: bar chart showcasing single appearances of topics, viewpoints and sources over the first 10 results for each query in Traditional SERPs and AI SERPs

Apart from the queries “Ukraine” and “Russia”, in which AI SERPs outrank Traditional SERP in terms of viewpoints, there is almost no difference between the result pages under analysis. Instead, Traditional SERPs even win in terms of topics and sources for the query “Russia” and “Israel”. Indeed, almost all sources analyzed in Traditional SERPs mirrored those retrieved in AI SERPs, with slight variations. Information generated by Bard

presents on the contrary much more variety, ranging – in just a few sentences – over six topics only for the query Israel and seven sources for the query Ukraine (Figure 11).

Figure 11: bar chart showcasing single appearances of topics, viewpoints and sources in snippets of text generated by Bard for each query

Also, in terms of viewpoints Bard provides in just a few words insights from several perspectives, ranging from political authorities to humanitarian organizations. However, it is crucial to note that a greater number of sources or viewpoints does not inherently equate to a higher quality of information. While Bard may offer an array of sources and perspectives, the credibility and authority of these sources need to be critically assessed.

In-depth analysis of SERP content

1. Topics: a mixed approach

The analysis of topic distribution for the queries Ukraine,” “Russia,” “Palestine,” and “Israel” across traditional and AI SERPs reveal insightful trends on how Generative AI, specifically Google’s Bard AI, curates content compared to traditional search algorithms (Figure 12, Figure 13).

Figure 12: doughnut charts showcasing topic distribution over first 10 results for the selected queries

Figure 13: matrix chart showcasing topic appearance in snippets of text generated by Bard over the selected queries

For all queries, there is a pronounced emphasis on the topic of “War” in both

traditional and AI SERPs, which is expected given the ongoing conflicts involving these countries (Figure 12). Interestingly, the “Politics” category experiences a higher focus for the query “Russia,” – only query for which the topic “War” is less present – possibly reflecting the algorithm’s ability to identify and present politically relevant information. In AI SERP this topic becomes slightly less relevant in favor of the topic “News”, which increases by 10% in presence compared to traditional SERP. Both for this query and the query “Ukraine” topics are less varied in AI SERPs than in traditional SERP. Traditional SERP also presents results on the thematic of “Help and support” that is not present in AI SERP. In general, topics distribution does not seem more balanced in AI SERPs than traditional SERPs. When analyzing the queries “Palestine” and “Israel,” the AI SERP for “Palestine” displays a greater emphasis on “News” compared to traditional SERPs, suggesting a stronger inclination towards providing users with current updates. While the distribution of topics for the query “Palestine” seems more balanced in AI SERP than in traditional SERP, the analysis for the query “Israel” under AI SERP showed a less varied range of topics, without the topic “Multiple”, an increase in “News” content, and the favoring of “Political” topics over “Historical” ones, confirming the inclination towards trending themes.

The matrix chart for topics generated by Bard AI underscores instead the generative model’s capacity to cover a range of topics (Figure 13). For instance, “Culture” – featured in almost all queries in Bard’s text – and “Economy” are topics not present both in traditional SERPs and AI SERPs when looking at top 10 results only. This indicates Bard’s ability to pull from a wider array of information, potentially enriching the user’s search experience with multidimensional insights. Moreover, it is to note that all queries generated text covering a wide variety of topics, with a minimum of three per query, like in the case of the query “Ukraine”. This is striking when compared to traditional SERPs topics distribution, where there is more space for more content and therefore a wider variety of topics is expected. Instead, for queries like “Palestine” only four topics were covered in a total of 10 search results – and two (i.e. “War” and “Overview”) dominated the SERP.

In the broader scope, these distributions underscore that while AI-powered search results might still be weighted towards current events and immediate news like traditional search results, the implementation of Bard AI can supplement with a varied content mix that encompasses overviews, political contexts, and historical backgrounds.

However, touching upon so many topics in just a few sentences – across almost all queries – also implies a synthesis of information that could potentially streamline diverse viewpoints into a cohesive narrative, which may or may not capture the complexity of the issues at hand.

2. Viewpoints: space for new perspectives

The analysis of viewpoints identified in the top 10 sources in traditional SERPs and AI-powered SERPs and in the text generated by Bard reveals interesting patterns in the curation of information made by algorithms powering AI-search (Figure 14, 15).

Figure 14: doughnut charts showcasing viewpoints distribution over first 10 results for the selected queries

Figure 15: matrix chart showcasing viewpoints appearance in snippets of text generated by Bard over the selected queries

It is interesting to note the consistent presence of “Informative” viewpoints across all AI SERP queries, which reinforces the idea that AI systems may be designed to offer users content that educates and informs (Figure 14). Moreover, AI-powered SERPs presents content from “Humanitarian” viewpoints across all queries, which is a crucial development as it can foster a more empathetic and socially conscious search experience. However, the consistent presence and, in some cases, the increase of “Topical” viewpoints in AI SERPs compared to traditional SERPs suggest that Generative AI might be prioritizing more recent and discussed issues. For the “Ukraine” query, the traditional SERP shows a greater emphasis on “Political” and “Topical” viewpoints, which reflects the current political tensions and the topical nature of the issue. On the other hand, the AI SERP shows a reduction in political viewpoints and an increase in “Informative” content, suggesting that AI is potentially prioritizing a more neutral or balanced presentation of information. In the case of “Russia”, both traditional and AI SERPs share a similar distribution across “Topical,” “Informative,” and “Political” categories, but with AI SERP leaning slightly more towards informative content. This could imply an attempt by the AI to provide a broader understanding of the topic beyond just the immediate news and political discourse. The “Palestine” query reveals a significant shift in the AI SERP, with a notable increase in “Humanitarian” viewpoints,

doubling the percentage found in traditional SERPs. This shift is essential, as it may represent an AI-driven effort to bring forward the human aspect of the conflict, which is often overshadowed by political and topical narratives, more in the spotlight. For “Israel,” both SERPs indicate a balance of viewpoints, but the AI SERP shows a slight increase in “Topical” content.

The analysis of viewpoints in text generated by Bard AI further highlights the generative model’s engagement with informative content across all queries (Figure 15). This uniform presence suggests that Bard AI prioritizes educational and neutral information, possibly aiming to provide a foundation for users to understand the broader context of their search queries. Across all queries, Bard AI tends to present “Informative” and “Political” viewpoints more frequently than “Topical” and “Humanitarian” ones. While this approach might put emphasis on the educational aims of the Generative AI implementation and might foster political engagement in the audience, at the same time it poses the risk of putting the users in front of an unbalanced array of viewpoints, narrow and polarized – resulting in the reinforcement of the status quo. Moreover, the representation of “Humanitarian” viewpoints only for the queries “Palestine” and “Ukraine” – therefore only for one side in the two conflicts interested by the double sets of queries – may suggest that AI systems still struggle to adequately represent the human impact of geopolitical issues. The ethical implications of this are significant, as it may affect the empathetic engagement of users with the subjects they are researching. In conclusion, while there is an evident attempt to diversify viewpoints and provide a more informative and less politically charged narrative, the nuanced distribution of these viewpoints highlights the complexity for AI-powered search of balancing information in a way that is both comprehensive and sensitive to the multifaceted nature of global issues.

3. Sources: evaluating information origins

The implementation of Generative AI on Google Search necessitates a thorough examination of its source selection to better assess its impact on information diversity. The data indicates a nuanced pattern of source citation (Figure 16).

Source appearances per query

over the first 10 results

QUERY “UKRAINE”

Traditional SERP

1. Wikipedia
2. AP News
3. The Guardian
4. Twitter
5. Britannica
6. CNN
7. CNBC
8. Politico
9. US Department of State
10. European Commission

AI SERP

1. Wikipedia
2. Twitter
3. AP News
4. US Department of State
5. The Guardian
6. Human Rights Watch
7. CNN
8. Al Jazeera
9. Politico
10. Britannica

QUERY “RUSSIA”

Traditional SERP

1. Wikipedia
2. Twitter
3. The Guardian
4. National Geographic Kids
5. President of Russia
6. US Department of State
7. AP News
8. Al Jazeera
9. The Russian Government
10. Wall Street Journal

AI SERP

1. Wikipedia
2. US Department of State
3. The Russian Government
4. Human Rights Watch
5. The Guardian
6. Al Jazeera
7. CIA
8. Britannica
9. Wall Street Journal
10. CNN

QUERY “PALESTINE”

Traditional SERP

1. Wikipedia
2. Britannica
3. Wikipedia
4. United Nations
5. Amnesty International
6. International Criminal Court
7. Al Jazeera
8. Al Jazeera
9. The Guardian
10. The Times of Israel

AI SERP

1. Wikipedia
2. United Nations
3. Amnesty International
4. Al Jazeera
5. Al Jazeera
6. Human Rights Watch
7. Unctad
8. Britannica
9. International Criminal Court
10. The Guardian

QUERY “ISRAEL”

Traditional SERP

1. Wikipedia
2. The Times of Israel
3. Amnesty International
4. The Guardian
5. Britannica
6. Twitter
7. US Department of State
8. Al Jazeera
9. BBC
10. The New York Times

AI SERP

1. Wikipedia
2. US Department of State
3. The Times of Israel
4. Amnesty International
5. NBC News
6. The New York Times
7. The Guardian
8. Al Jazeera
9. Al Jazeera
10. Britannica

Figure 16: bar charts showcasing sources distribution over first 10 results for the selected queries

In traditional SERPs, there is a notable reliance on established news outlets, governmental sources, and recognized encyclopedias. However, in AI SERPs, a slightly broader spectrum emerges, characterized by the inclusion of human rights–focused sources, such as Human Rights Watch across almost all queries, which introduces an additional dimension of humanitarian discourse. While the AI SERP for “Russia” reflect a diverse array of perspectives by incorporating sources from within the country, like the Russian

government, alongside international human rights documentation, searching for “Ukraine” returns more results published by media outlets like AP News. When considering the “Palestine” and “Israel” queries, both traditional and AI SERPs exhibit a range of sources from global news agencies to international organizations. However, AI SERPs present a slightly more limited array of sources, considering that for both queries the news website Al Jazeera ranks twice. There are several sources that repeat across different queries in both Traditional and AI SERPs: Wikipedia, Al Jazeera, The Guardian. It is also interesting to note that for the query “Palestine” Wikipedia ranks twice in traditional SERP, both for the entry “Palestine (region)” and for the entry “State of Palestine”. While the removal of this second entry this may appear to enrich the diversity of sources by leaving more space to other voices, it also introduces the potential to inadvertently constrain users’ perspectives. The nuanced distinction between these entries is crucial; users may not fully grasp the implications of this differentiation, which reflects the complex socio–political dimensions of the term “Palestine”.

The analysis of Bard AI-generated texts reveals a consistent reference to Wikipedia across all examined queries, suggesting a foundational reliance on established knowledge databases (Figure 17).

Figure 17: matrix chart showcasing sources appearance in snippets of text generated by Bard over the selected queries

Additionally, the consistent presence of sources such as Al Jazeera and the US Department of State points to Bard AI’s recognition of the importance of authoritative sources in crafting comprehensive overviews. The inclusion of human rights organizations – like Human Rights Watch and Palestine Children’s Relief Fund – in the AI-curated texts indicates an algorithmic awareness of the ethical and humanitarian dimensions that are

integral to the understanding of geopolitical issues. This aspect of source selection by Bard AI has the potential to foster a more empathetic engagement with global events among users. In general, while AI SERPs might in some instances constrain perspectives, the addition of Google Bard increases the opportunities for a broader selection of sources. This diversity is crucial as it could contribute to a more nuanced and multifaceted narrative, enhancing the richness of perspectives available to users.

Discussion

Throughout the exploration of information diversity on Bard-powered Google Search, this study has ventured into a complex interplay of technology, knowledge acquisition practices, and societal impact. At the heart of this investigation lies the query: How does the implementation of Generative AI through Google Bard in Google Search results impact the information diversity of the results? This discussion seeks to intertwine the findings of this study with the foundational concepts delineated above (i.e., information diversity, relevance, filter bubbles, and privileging mechanisms). These concepts serve as critical lenses through which the implications of AI-implementation on Google Search are dissected, offering insights into the nuanced ways this technology might reshape our digital information ecosystem. The following section not only engages in a reflective analysis of the research results, but also situates them within the broader context of the domains of Critical Search Engine Studies, Platform Studies, and Critical AI Studies. This synthesis aims to uncover the multifaceted dynamics at play in the evolving narrative of AI-driven search engines.

Information diversity in the era of Google Bard

Central to this paper is the investigation of information diversity within the domain of search engines, particularly the dichotomy between traditional Google Search and a cutting-edge version of it, powered by new generative tool owned by the company, Bard. This study's findings expose a nuanced landscape where Google Bard recalibrates the balance of information diversity in search results. These novel dynamics are reflected in the range and variance of content presented by Google Bard in contrast to traditional search engines. The results indicate that AI-powered search engines indeed offer a broader spectrum of topics. However, this variation does not necessarily guarantee a more profound depth or breadth in perspectives. This observation is supported by the findings by Steiner et al. (2020) on information diversity, suggesting that while diverse information is attainable through search engines, "there is a noticeable risk of not getting diverse (and comprehensive) information

when considering only the first result” (Steiner et al. 2020, 227). This insight deeply resonates with the findings of the current study, which similarly indicates that the surface-level expansion of diversity in AI-powered Google Search does not necessarily translate into a substantial enhancement in the depth of information or the richness of viewpoints. This finding challenges the anticipated outcomes of AI integration in search engines, prompting a reevaluation of the effectiveness of AI in delivering a truly diverse information landscape.

Also, relevance is seen through a new lens in the era of AI-powered search. The findings suggest a paradigm shift from traditional metrics of popularity and newsworthiness to a more nuanced, contextually-aware interpretation of relevance by AI systems like Google Bard. However, the analysis revealed that, despite the broad spectrum of topics generated by AI, the underlying viewpoints were often aligned with mainstream narratives, potentially sidelining alternative or counter-narratives. For instance, in the analysis conducted on the search query “Ukraine” through AI-powered Google Search, it was observed that while there was an apparent increase in the variety of topics covered by Bard, the AI-powered top 10 results still predominantly highlighted current news and popular narratives, reflecting Gillespie’s notion of algorithmic relevance being tied to metrics like popularity (2014). This observation is a practical manifestation of concerns around relevance where algorithmic selection, even in AI-driven systems, might not fully escape the constraints of traditional relevance paradigms. This raises critical questions about the balance between AI’s efficiency in information retrieval and its capacity to foster a comprehensive and diverse informational environment.

The phenomenon of filter bubbles, as described by Pariser (2011), is also pertinent in the context of AI-driven search results. The study’s findings hint at the potential for AI systems to unwittingly perpetuate these bubbles, contrary to the anticipated role of AI in breaking down closed information system. An example from the analysis conducted in this paper is identified in the examination of search results for the query “Palestine” in Bard-powered results. The AI-generated top 10 results predominantly surfaced news articles and perspectives that aligned with mainstream narratives on the conflict. While these results provided a breadth of information, they notably lacked diverse viewpoints, particularly those representing less dominant narratives or local perspectives. Moreover, while AI-powered results could integrate Humanitarian viewpoints compared to traditional SERPs, this representation of Humanitarian viewpoints was predominantly observed for “Palestine” and

“Ukraine”, but not equivalently for the related queries “Israel” and “Russia”. This disparity may indicate that AI systems, like Google Bard, struggle to represent the human impact of geopolitical issues in a balanced manner. Such a tendency aligns with Pariser’s notion of filter bubbles, where search algorithms, in their quest for relevance and personalization, might inadvertently create a skewed narrative (2011). This limits exposure to a more diverse range of voices and inadvertently creates an information echo chamber. The search results, tailored to what the AI algorithm presumed to be relevant or popular, excluded a range of alternative viewpoints and narratives, thus limiting the exposure of users to a more comprehensive understanding of the issue. This observed trend underscores the importance of critically assessing the role of AI in reinforcing existing patterns of information consumption and exposure.

Furthermore, this study explores how the implementation of AI technologies such as Google Bard not only contributes to the formation of filter bubbles but also potentially reinforces existing privileging mechanisms, as highlighted by Roger (2023). Roger’s discourse (2023) on the prioritization of certain types of information becomes particularly relevant here. In this study, privileging mechanisms become evident – for instance - through the identification of recurrent citations of Wikipedia across various queries. Google Bard often cites the same websites multiple times, like Britannica, Al Jazeera, Wikipedia. This happens not only in top 10 results, but also as a reference for the text snippet generated at the top of AI SERPs. In the case of Wikipedia, the nature of the online encyclopedia means that it tends to provide a generalist and often sanitized overview, which might not fully capture the nuanced viewpoints or the latest developments, particularly in rapidly evolving geopolitical situations. These results suggest that while AI-powered search engines like Google Bard might introduce new sources and perspectives, they may still uphold traditional privileging mechanisms, thus not fully resolving the issues of representation and bias prevalent in search engines.

In summary, this study’s findings around the implementation of Google Bard in Google Search paint a complex picture of the evolving role of AI in search engines. The promise of AI in enhancing information diversity and relevance is partially met, while still perpetuating the reality of challenges like filter bubbles and privileging mechanisms. Therefore, a continued critical examination of AI’s impact on our digital information landscape is necessary.

Bridging the gap between Critical Search Engine Studies, Platform Studies and Critical AI Studies

In examining the impact of AI on search engines, this paper intersects with the field of Critical Search Engine Studies. The findings of this study, particularly in relation to the role of AI in shaping search results, bear a notable comparison to the seminal work of Noble (2018) on the biases inherent in search engine algorithms. While Noble's research sheds light on the pre-existing gender and racial biases within traditional search algorithms, the present work extends the conversation to the realm of AI, exploring how biases are perpetuated and altered in an AI-driven context. The comparative analysis reveals both congruities and divergences, suggesting that while AI has the potential to mitigate some biases, it may also introduce new complexities and challenges. For example, the comparison between traditional SERPs topic distribution and AI SERPs for the queries "Russia" and "Israel" revealed that AI SERPs presented less topic, resonating with the concerns already expressed by Noble on search results' lack of diversity and perpetuation of biases (2018).

This research also provides insights into the evolution of search algorithms. It brings to light the transition from traditional, keyword-based algorithms to more sophisticated, AI-driven models that promise greater relevance and diversity in search results. As we step into the era of AI-powered search, there is a noticeable shift from algorithmic accuracy and speed to the contextual understanding and nuanced presentation of search results. This not only marks a distinct phase in the technological advancement of search engines but also reflects a deeper change in the relationship between users and information.

In delving into the nuances of AI-powered search engines, this research is also relevant to the domain of Platform Studies. The observations on Google Bard's role in shaping search results invites a comparison to the foundational concepts articulated by Jean Burgess (2021) on the co-evolution of platform technologies and user cultures. While Burgess's work (2021) offers insights into the broader dynamics of digital media platforms, this study extends the analysis to AI's influence on these platforms, particularly examining how Google Bard, as a platform, recalibrates content creation and distribution. The juxtaposition suggests that, like the transformative influence of platforms described by Burgess (2021), AI can significantly reshape user experience and information dissemination. At the same time, it would introduce complexities and challenges typical of digital platforms, like concerns about algorithmic transparency and complexity (Gillespie 2014). AI-powered

Google Search algorithm tended to prioritize current events and popular narratives, demonstrating a potential inclination towards trending topics over comprehensive overviews for the query “Ukraine”. This observation suggests that while Bard can potentially enhance information accessibility and diversity, it also risks reinforcing the traditional news cycle and popular narratives, a critical issue in Platform Studies.

Finally, in the context of Google Bard’s integration into search engines, this study provides significant insights for the field of Critical AI Studies. The observations made in this paper regarding AI’s role in shaping and influencing search results resonate strongly with the critical perspectives of scholars like David J. Gunkel (2012) and Kate Crawford (2021), who have explored the ethical and societal dimensions of artificial intelligence. While these scholars lay the groundwork for understanding AI’s broader impacts, this study specifically probes into how such ethical challenges surface in AI-driven search engines. For example, the observed struggle in an equal representation of viewpoints for the queries “Palestine” and “Israel” reflects Crawford’s concerns about data bias (2021). Again, the tendency of Bard to prioritize mainstream narratives for the query “Ukraine” echoes Gunkel’s ethical questioning of AI’s societal role (2012).

Moreover, this research sheds light on the evolving trajectory of AI in practical applications. The transition from basic AI models to the more advanced, contextually aware algorithms of Google Bard, which promise enhanced personalization and relevance, is pivotal. This study’s findings, such as the nuanced portrayal of topics and the challenges in achieving a diverse range of perspectives in search results, underscore the significant role AI plays in redefining user engagement and information access on digital platforms. These observations align with the concerns in Critical AI Studies about ensuring AI technologies advance in capabilities, but also align ethically and socially, thereby contributing constructively to the digital information landscape.

In conclusion, this discussion navigated the multifaceted implications of AI integration into search engines, viewed through the prisms of Critical Search Engine Studies, Platform Studies, and Critical AI Studies. It underscores the continuity of mainstream biases into AI-powered Google Search, contributing to Critical Search Engine Studies, and raises important questions about algorithmic transparency and content diversity, central to Platform

Studies. Furthermore, the ethical and societal implications of Bard, as discussed in Critical AI Studies, expose concerns about data bias and the ethical responsibilities of AI deployment.

Conclusion

This paper embarked on a critical journey to explore the transformative impact of Generative AI on information diversity within Google Search results, with a particular focus on Google Bard. The crucial question guiding this study was: How does the implementation of Generative AI through Google Bard in Google Search results impact the information diversity of the results? The aim of this research was not only to understand the evolving dynamics in the digital landscape, where AI technologies like Google Bard reshape the way information is curated and presented, its diversity and quality, but also to make significant contributions to the broader discourse in distinct yet interconnected academic domains. These domains include Critical Search Engine Studies, where the research sheds light on the nuanced role of AI in search engine evolution; Platform Studies, highlighting how digital platforms are being redefined by AI; and Critical AI Studies, where it addresses vital concerns regarding AI's societal implications.

The analysis of this paper underscored the intricate dynamics that Generative AI introduces into the curation of search engine results. While traditional SERPs exhibit a tendency towards established news outlets and governmental sources, Bard AI augments the diversity of sources, albeit with room for improvement in offering a balanced spectrum of perspectives. The findings suggest that Bard AI in particular has the potential to democratize information retrieval by broadening the array of sources and viewpoints, thereby enhancing the overall diversity of information. However, there is a critical need for ongoing scrutiny to ensure that this AI-driven curation does not inadvertently introduce new biases or narrow the scope of discourse. It was found that Bard, while extending the range of topics covered, sometimes streamlined complex narratives into more generalized overviews, potentially simplifying multifaceted issues. These findings suggest that while Bard AI marks a step towards diversifying search engine results, it simultaneously retains certain biases and limitations inherent in AI-driven content curation. The implications of these findings are multifaceted. On one hand, the AI-driven curation suggests a promising avenue for exposing users to a wider array of information, potentially breaking down the barriers of traditional filter bubbles. However, the persistence of mainstream biases and the continued reliance on popular narratives indicate a more complex reality. This study's insights suggest that while

AI has the potential to enrich information diversity, its current implementation may not fully realize it. Instead, AI-powered search seems to reshape the contours of information diversity without fundamentally solving its core challenges. These findings invite a critical reassessment of the role of AI in managing the digital information landscape, emphasizing the need for a deeper understanding of how AI algorithms curate, prioritize, and present information to users. In essence, the study prompts a reevaluation of the promise of AI in delivering a truly diverse and unbiased information ecosystem.

The broader societal and ethical implications of this research are profound. This study reveals how AI-driven search engines like Google Bard can subtly shape public discourse, influencing knowledge acquisition and cultural understanding. This research underscores the need for tech companies like Google to invest in refining AI algorithms to enhance both the breadth and depth of information diversity. For policymakers and regulators, these findings emphasize the importance of developing frameworks that ensure responsible AI use in information dissemination. The study also contributes to the broader discourse on digital literacy, suggesting that users need to be aware of the strengths and limitations of AI-powered search engines in their quest for informed knowledge and diverse viewpoints. This study offers a novel understanding of AI's role in search engines, highlighting the balance between algorithmic efficiency and information diversity. These insights are vital for developers and researchers, offering a foundation for future innovations in AI-driven search technologies that are more ethically aligned and culturally responsive. Finally, this research aligns with and extends current discussions on the nuanced roles of LLMs and chatbots, particularly concerning their political leanings and representational diversity. It underscores the evolving landscape where AI is not just a technological tool, but an active agent within information narratives, reflecting and potentially influencing societal biases.

While comprehensive, this study has limitations, including its focus on conflict-related queries and the specific context of Google Bard. Future research could broaden the scope by examining diverse query types and other AI-driven search engines to validate these findings. Additionally, incorporating user experience studies could provide deeper insights into how individuals interact with and perceive AI-curated content. This research advocates for a collaborative effort among various stakeholders to develop AI technologies that are both innovative and ethically sound. As we move forward, it is essential to balance technological

innovation with a commitment to foster an information ecosystem that is diverse, reliable, and reflective of the multifaceted nature of global discourse.

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Appendix

Code Book

Topics: The main subject or theme of the search result

Code	Description	Example
Overview	Overview around a query, covering a range of subjects	Wikipedia page on “Israel”
War	Content focused on specific conflicts, military actions, and related humanitarian issues	Amnesty International report on “Israel and Occupied Palestinian Territories 2022”
Culture	Discusses the arts, beliefs, customs, and social behavior of a society	Snippet of text written by Bard AI, detailing the cultural aspects of Palestine
Politics	Deals with political affairs, governance, policy-making, and discussions about state and international relations	Politico article on Ukraine’s response to Russian power cuts
Help and Support	Focuses on aid, relief efforts, and support initiatives in response to crises or conflicts	European Commission’s page on aid to Ukraine
Geography	Content covering geographical information, such as physical characteristics and demography	Snippet of text from Wikipedia in the content above the fold in traditional SERP providing geographical information about Ukraine
History	Provides historical context or discusses historical events	United Nation’s article on the history of the Question of Palestine
Multiple	Content spans multiple topics and does not fit neatly into a single category	Twitter feed “@Russia” under “Traditional SERP” showing various types of content
Human Rights	Issues related to the fundamental rights and freedoms entitled to all individuals	Reference from Bard AI to the human rights violations by the Russian government
Economy	Content that discusses economic matters, financial markets, trade, or economic policies.	Text generated by Bard mentioning Israel’s financial hub, Tel Aviv
Religion	Content focused on beliefs, practices, organizational aspects, or spiritual matters of faiths.	Text generated by Bard mentioning the high amount of sacred sites present in Israel

Viewpoints: The perspective or stance, represented by the source publishing the result, together with the nature of the result itself

Viewpoint	Description	Example
Informative	Aiming at presenting facts or information neutrally without bias or opinion.	Wikipedia tend to represent information in a neutral way as an online encyclopedia
Topical	Source interested into and writing about events occuring in the news, trending. Usually from news organizations or media outlets	Articles with war updates by Al Jazeera
Humanitarian	Source from specific humanitarian organizations, publishing on human welfare, often emphasizing aid, relief, or rights.	“Israel and Occupied Palestinian Territories 2022” from Amnesty International
Political	Source from a government website or organization, often discussing political topics	The Russian Government’s official site
Incriminatory	Implies blame or responsibility, often in a legal or moral context. Source can be varied. Often partisan.	Youtube video against Russia